

A REVIEW: EXTRACTION OF VALUABLE PHYTOCONSTITUENTS USING COLD-MACERATION METHOD WITH DIFFERENT POLAR AND NONPOLAR SOLVENTS FOR THEIR PHARMACOLOGICAL ACTIVITIES

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ABSTRACT

The extraction of phytochemicals from medicinal plants is an important step in the production of plant-based medications. Cold maceration remains one of the most popular extraction processes due to its easy of use, low cost and ability to maintain thermolabile bioactive chemicals. This paper investigates the efficacy of the cold maceration method for extracting pharmacologically active phytochemicals utilising various solvents, including polar and non-polar solvents. The choice of solvent has a major impact on the yield, content and biological activity of the extracted phytoconstituent. Polar solvents like methanol, hydro-ethanol are useful in extracting phenolics, flavonoids, glycosides and tannins, but non-polar solvents like n-hexane and petroleum ether are more ideal for alkaloids, terpenoids and lipophilic compounds. This review also emphasises the importance of solvent polarity, maceration Operiod, plant material-to-solvent ratio and ambient

temperature in optimising the extraction process. Comparative pharmacological investigations reveal that cold maceration extracts exhibit a diverse range of biological activities, including antibacterial, antioxidant, anti-inflammatory, anticancer, and antidiabetic effects.

KEYWORDS: cold-maceration method, Methanol, Hydro-ethanol, N-hexane, Petroleum ether.

1. INTRODUCTION

1.1. Traditional Use of Medicinal Plants in Human Healthcare

The medicinal properties of plants have been used in China and India to treat various human health problems for centuries, dating back to pre-civilization times. The components of this plant have been utilized for a long time and possess a wide range of therapeutic properties. Approximately 30–50% of the indigenous people who live in remote and unreachable sections of the world's woods rely on medicinal plants for their basic medical needs (Maurya *et al.*, 2022). Several factors result from the availability and cost of traditional medicine as a form of care in the primary healthcare system of resource-poor areas. Plants have been the main source of medicinal items used to treat human ailments since the dawn of humanity. Before recorded history, people were more or less aware of the properties of the plants around them since they had learned to recognize and use them for food, clothing, shelter and fuel.

1.2. Phytochemicals: Classification, Functions and Health Benefits

Phytochemicals, derived from the Greek term phyto, meaning plant, are physiologically active, naturally occurring chemical compounds present in plants. These molecules have a greater positive impact on human health than macronutrients and micronutrients. Phytochemicals or phytocompounds have been categorized as primary and secondary components according to their function in plant metabolism.^[2] Common sugars, amino acids, proteins, purines, pyrimidines and other primary ingredients that are directly involved in plant growth and development include amino acids, purines and pyrimidines of nucleic acids. Other plant compounds, including curcumines, saponins, phenolics, flavonoids, lignans, plant steroids and glucosides, which are indirectly involved in growth and development, are considered secondary ingredients.^[3] Secondary phytocompounds have key qualities that can help prevent or treat several common ailments, even though they do not contain any necessary nutrients or are needed by the human body to support life.

1.3. Methods of extracting medicinal plants that priorities cold-maceration method

A study on medicinal plants^[3] starts with pre-extraction and extraction techniques, which are important steps in the extraction of bioactive components from plant materials. Extraction is the process of separating the various components of a plant that are medicinally effective

using certain solvents and accepted practices. All extraction procedures have the same goal: to separate the plant's soluble metabolites from its insoluble cellular components. Some of the basic crude must be further processed. Maceration, infusion, percolation, decoction, Soxhlet extractors, and ultrasound-assisted extraction machines are the most frequently used extraction techniques. Among these methods, we chose the cold maceration technique.^[4] In small research settings, maceration extraction is a widely used conventional method. The process of cold maceration, widely used in the production of red wine, has implications for logistics, finances, and product quality. The plant material was coarsely powdered and placed in a stoppered container with a solvent. The mixture was allowed to rest at room temperature for at least three days while being constantly stirred. The plant cell wall is intended to be weakened and ruptured during processing to release soluble phytochemicals.

1.4. The usual condition for maceration method.

Particle size	Coarse to medium powder to increase surface area without producing fines that complicate filtration
Solvent-to-solid ratio	Commonly 5:1 to 20:1 (mL/g) depending on matrix and solvent
Time	From 24 hr up to several days with intermittent agitation in some protocol use 24-72 hr
Temperature	20-25 °C
Agitation	Periodic shaking or mechanical stirring speeds equilibrium

1.5. Filtration and solvent removal

The extraction of phytochemicals is heavily dependent on the solvents used. Low toxicity, ease of evaporation at low heat, promotion of quick physiological absorption of the extract, preservation action and inability to induce the extract to complex or dissociate are all qualities of a suitable solvent in plant extractions. The choice of solvent is influenced by the amount of phytochemicals to be extracted, extraction rate, diversity of compounds extracted, diversity of inhibitory compounds extracted, ease of handling the extracts after extraction, solvent toxicity in the bioassay process and potential health risks posed by the extractants. The planned use of the extract affects the choice of solvent. Generally, there are two types of solvents: polar and nonpolar. Polar solvents generate a better yield of phytochemicals than non-polar solvents because of their larger dipole moments.

1.6. Solvent polarity: classification and common bioactives targets

Solvent polarity is the single most important factor determining which classes of phytochemicals are extracted. Common solvents used across polarity ranges.

Nonpolar solvents: n-hexane, petroleum ether. Targets: fixed oils, fatty acids, nonpolar terpenoids, sterols, carotenoids.

Polar solvents: Ethanol, methanol, water and methanol-water mixture. Targets: phenolic acids, flavonoids glycosides, tannins, alkaloids (depending on base/acid state), glycosides, polysaccharides.

Solvent choice is thus matched to the expected chemistry of the target phytoconstituents. Methanol and ethanol are widely used because they dissolve a broad range of polar constituents and are compatible with many analytical workflows; water extracts very polar materials but can co-extract sugars, proteins and large carbohydrate matrices.

Table I: Shows the polar and non-polar used for the extraction of active phytochemicals.

Polar and Non-polar Solvents			
1.Methanol	2. Hydro-ethanol	1. n-hexane	2. Petroleum ether
Polyphenols	Polyphenols		Alkaloids
Terpenoids	Terpenoids		Terpenoids
Saponins	saponins		
Lactones	Tannins		
Anthocyanins	Amino acids Carbohydrates Glycosides Flavonoids phenones		

1.7. Solvents polarity influences extraction yield and bioactivity

Many empirical research have found polarity-dependent variations in overall yield, phenolic/flavonoid content, and antioxidant or other bioactivities. In many plant matrices, highly polar solvents produce a higher mass yield (because they solubilise sugars and polar metabolites), whereas medium polarity solvents may concentrate antioxidant polyphenols more effectively; nonpolar solvents produce lower mass yields but concentrate lipophilic bioactives (essential oils, lipids) with distinct bioactivities (antimicrobial, anti-inflammatory). Several comparative studies and systematic reviews have found that utilising a panel of solvents (consecutive or parallel extraction) provides the most comprehensive phytochemical coverage and the highest possibility of linking certain pharmacologies to specific fractions.

Table II: Showing polar and non-polar solvents with their boiling point and dipole moment.

Sl No	Polar Solvents	Dipole	Boiling point	Non-polar solvents	Dipole Moment	Boiling point
1	Water	1.85	100	Petroleum ether	0	60 ^o C
2	Methanol	1.7	64.4	Hexane	0.08	68.70C
3	Ethanol	1.69	1.15	Chloroform	1.15	0C
4	Acetone	2.88	56	Chloro benzene	1.69	131.7
5	Ethyl acetate	1.88	40	Diethyl	1.15	34.5
6	2- propanol	1.58	82.5	Dichoromethane	1.6	39.6

2. Methanol was used as a solvent with cold-maceration method

Methanol is one of the most commonly used solvents for extracting phytochemicals due to its strong polarity and high extraction efficiency. It has been applied in various studies to obtain bioactive compounds with significant pharmacological properties.

The *Lantana camara* plant was studied to determine its potential antidiarrheal properties. Castor oil was used to induce diarrhea, while the plant's bioactive compounds were extracted using cold maceration with 80% methanol. The results showed that the methanol extract had strong antidiarrheal potential.^[5] Similarly,^[6] extracted bioactive compounds from *Newbouldia laevis* (Bignoniaceae) using methanol with cold maceration method and the extract exhibited strong antihyperglycemic activity. According to,^[7] *Combretum hypopilinum* has diverse therapeutic applications, including treatment of gastrointestinal disorders as well as cholagogic, diuretic and purgative conditions. Methanol extracts obtained through cold maceration revealed notable antidiarrheal activity and valuable phytochemicals.^[8] investigated *Napoleona vogelii* Hook & Planch (Lecythidaceae) for antidiabetic and hypolipidemic effects in alloxan-induced diabetic models. Phytochemicals were extracted using 70% methanol via cold maceration. The extract exhibited hypoglycemic potential and contained important flavonoids, glycosides, tannins, and other quality phytochemicals. Likewise,^[9] extracted phytochemicals from *Lophira lanceolata* (Ochnaceae) using methanol and cold maceration method to evaluate acute toxicity (LD50), antiplasmodial activity and antioxidant capacity. Antioxidant activity was assessed using DPPH, hydrogen peroxide scavenging, free radical scavenging and reducing ability assays, while antiplasmodial activity was tested using a rodent parasitemia model. The plant extract demonstrated significant antioxidant and antiplasmodial activity.

As per.^[10] methanol and ethanol were used to extract bioactive compounds from *Musa paradisiaca* (banana) tepals via cold maceration. Methanol extracts (from tepal meat and skin) showed greater nitric oxide scavenging activity and anti-inflammatory properties than ethanol extracts.^[11] extracted phytochemicals from *Callicarpa arborea* leaves with methanol using cold maceration and reported that the extracts exhibited antioxidant activity through different assays, suggesting their usefulness in preventing infections and degenerative diseases. Similarly,^[12] extracted phytochemicals from *Solanum lycopersicum* (L.) using methanol and water. Methanol extracts displayed significant antibacterial activity in vitro compared to water extracts.^[13] reported that methanol was used in cold maceration to extract bioactive compounds from *Anabasis articulata* stems. Antioxidant activity was tested using DPPH and radical scavenging assays, while anti-angiogenesis was assessed with a rat aorta ring test. The methanol extract showed notable antioxidant and anti-angiogenic activities compared to other solvents. According to^[14] *Mikania micrantha* leaves were extracted with methanol via cold maceration, yielding high phenolic content and strong antioxidant activity. In another study,^[15] extracted phytochemicals from the stems, barks and fractions of *Schwa infurthiona F. Hoffm* (Ochnaceae) using methanol and other solvents. FRAP and DPPH assays revealed that methanol extracts exhibited stronger antioxidant activity than those from other solvents.

Cold maceration with methanol was also applied to *Euphorbia tirucalli*, along with petroleum ether, chloroform, and aqueous solvents.^[16] Tested antifungal activity against *Aspergillus niger* and *Candida albicans* strains and found methanol and aqueous extracts to be the most effective. Similarly,^[17] reported that people in northern regions consumed *Castanopsis costata* (*C. costata*) as an antioxidant dietary supplement. Methanol extracts of its leaves contained important phytochemicals and antioxidant properties comparable to vitamin C.

Two plants, *Solanum unigram* and *Solanum xanthocarpum*, were extracted using methanol and water via cold maceration.^[18] evaluated their antimicrobial, antioxidant, antidiabetic, and hemolytic activities. Methanol extracts demonstrated higher free phenol content, strong inhibition of *E. coli*, and significant antioxidant activity.

Henna (*Lawsonia inermis*) leaves, traditionally used as dye, were extracted using cold maceration with methanol, water, and ethyl acetate. According to.^[19] methanol and water extracts contained a notably high concentration of tannins, suitable for leather tanning and coloring. In another study,^[20] used Soxhlet and cold maceration with several solvents to

extract *Moringa stenopetala* leaves (Moringaceae). Methanol and its aqueous fraction significantly reduced both central and peripheral pain and inflammation, indicating analgesic and anti-inflammatory effects.

The bioactive compounds of *Plectranthus amboinicus* leaves were extracted with methanol using cold maceration.^[21] reported that these extracts had the highest phenolic and flavonoid content, strong DPPH scavenging activity, and superior antimicrobial properties against tested pathogens. Similarly,^[22] extracted phytochemicals from *Euphorbia heterophylla* and *Tithonia diversifolia* using methanol via cold maceration. The methanol extracts showed significant inhibition of *Salmonella typhi* and *Pseudomonas aeruginosa*. According to,^[23] methanol cold maceration of *Coldenia procumbens* Linn revealed phytochemical content and antioxidant activity through reducing power and hydrogen peroxide radical scavenging assays.

Bryophyllum pinnatum (Crassulaceae) was studied for antidiarrheal and antioxidant properties.^[24] extracted its bioactive compounds with 80% methanol via cold maceration and found significant activity using DPPH and FRAP assays. Similarly,^[25] extracted phytochemicals from *Agapanthus africanus* leaves with 80% methanol. Results confirmed acute toxicity and strong anti-inflammatory activity. In another study,^[26] evaluated *Lupinus arboreus* extracts prepared with methanol for antioxidant and free radical scavenging activity.

After 72 hours of cold maceration, the methanol extract exhibited strong therapeutic value.^[27] compared aqueous, methanol, ethanol, and acetone extracts of *Paederia foetida* obtained by cold maceration and found methanol to yield the highest phenolic content and strongest antioxidant activity in DPPH and ABTS assays.

According to,^[28] methanol was used to extract phytochemicals from *Napoleona vogelii* leaves (Lecythidaceae). The extract showed strong antidiabetic efficacy in alloxan-induced diabetes and hypolipidemic activity. Similarly,^[29] extracted bioactive compounds from *Citrullus colocynthis* using solvents such as butanol, methanol, chloroform, ethanol, and hexane.

Methanol and butanol extracts, being more polar, contained significant phytochemicals.^[30] extracted *Thespesia populnea* phytochemicals with methanol, revealing the presence of carbohydrates, phenolics, flavonoids, alkaloids, and glycosides. Further studies confirmed methanol's effectiveness.^[31] extracted *Garcinia kola*, *Kola auminate*, and *Kola vera* using

99.5% methanol via cold maceration and detected saponins, glycosides, volatile oils, steroids, and alkaloids.^[32] studied aerial parts of *Semenovia suffruticosa* using methanol cold maceration. The extract showed antioxidant activity and tumor cell-specific cytotoxicity, confirmed through DPPH, agar disc, and MTT assays.^[33] extracted *Pinus halepensis* and *Quercus ilex* L. using methanol cold maceration. The extracts demonstrated antioxidant, anti-hemolytic, and genoprotective properties due to high phenolic and flavonoid content.

Stachytarpheta indica (Verbenaceae) was extracted with methanol, and the extract confirmed the presence of alkaloids, saponins, tannins, anthraquinones, phenolics, and flavonoids.^[34] It exhibited strong anti-inflammatory activity. Similarly,^[35] evaluated *Boswellia dalzielii* (frankincense), extracted with methanol, followed by fractionation using n-hexane, chloroform, ethyl lactate, and n-butanol. The methanol extract showed significant antidiabetic activity in alloxan-induced diabetic rats and contained saponins, tannins, and terpenoids.

According to,^[36] *Cardiospermum halicacabum* extracts obtained with methanol demonstrated strong antioxidant activity, confirmed through GC-MS analysis and DPPH assays.^[37] extracted *Hibiscus sabdariffa* (Roselle) using methanol via cold maceration and found significant antioxidant activity, particularly in the calyx, leaves, and stem. Similarly,^[38] compared extracts of *Fumaria officinalis* leaves prepared with methanol, petroleum ether, and chloroform. Methanol produced higher levels of phenolics and flavonoids, making it the most effective solvent. According to,^[39] *Thuja occidentalis* extracts obtained with methanol displayed substantial phenolic and flavonoid content, strong antioxidant activity, and significant antimicrobial activity against resistant bacteria, comparable to antibiotics such as ofloxacin and amphotericin B.^[40] studied *Rhododendron arboreum* (Ericaceae) flowers using 80% methanol and other solvents. Methanol extracts had higher total phenolic content (107.46 ± 8.74 mg/g RE) and greater antioxidant activity compared to ethanolic extracts.

Achyranthes aspera Linn bioactive compounds were extracted with methanol using cold maceration by.^[41] The methanol extract showed notable antioxidant, antibacterial, and thrombolytic properties. According to,^[42] *Fadogia cienkowskii* extracts obtained with methanol exhibited high total flavonoid and phenolic content (TFC and TPC) and strong antioxidant activity. Finally,^[43] extracted phytochemicals from *Tinospora cordifolia* (gurjo) with methanol using cold maceration. The methanol extract demonstrated significant antioxidant and cytotoxic activity, as well as strong antimicrobial activity against *Streptococcus* strains.

3. Hydro-ethanol was used as a solvent with cold-maceration method

Water, ethanol, methanol, and acetone are the most commonly used solvents for preparing extracts with strong antioxidant activity. However, for food applications or when low toxicity is required, ethanol–water mixtures (hydro-ethanol) are considered the most suitable solvents.

These combinations are widely employed for extracting phenolic compounds from medicinal plants.

According to,^[44] bioactive compounds from *Anabasis aretioides* Coss. & Moq. (Chenopodiaceae) were extracted using cold maceration and Soxhlet methods. Antioxidant activity was evaluated through different assays, and antibacterial activity was assessed using disc diffusion. Results showed that cold maceration extracts had higher antioxidant and antibacterial activity compared to Soxhlet extracts. As noted by,^[45] solvents play a crucial role in phytoconstituent extraction. Hydro-ethanol, being a polar solvent, was used to extract bioactive compounds from *Citrullus colocynthis* (C. colocynthis). These extracts obtained through cold maceration demonstrated the ability to lower blood glucose levels.^[46] reported that *Cardiospermum* L. phytochemicals were extracted using ethanol by the cold maceration method. The ethanol extract showed valuable antibacterial, antioxidant, analgesic, vasodepressant, and anti-inflammatory properties. A comparative study by^[47] examined the yield and composition of *Bryophyllum* phytochemicals extracted by Soxhlet and cold maceration. The cold maceration method, using ethanol, produced a higher yield and a more diverse range of useful bioactive components compared to Soxhlet extraction. Similarly,^[48] extracted phytochemicals from *Momordica cymbalaria* (Cucurbitaceae) using several techniques to determine phenolic and flavonoid contents, as well as antioxidant and antidiabetic activities. Cold maceration extracts showed stronger activity than Soxhlet extracts.

Phytochemicals have significant medicinal and pharmacological benefits. For instance, *Thymelaea hirsuta* was collected from different geographical regions, and its bioactive compounds were extracted by both Soxhlet and cold maceration methods. According to,^[49] cold maceration extracts had the highest phenolic content, which was strongly correlated with antioxidant activity. In another study,^[50] extracted phytochemicals from *Anisochilus carnosus* (L.F) against the gastric pathogen *Helicobacter pylori* using a water–ethanol solvent via cold maceration. The extract showed stronger inhibitory activity against *H. pylori* than Soxhlet extracts.

The medicinal and pharmacological properties of *Strobilanthes ciliatus* Nees have also been investigated. According to,^[51] this plant possesses hepatoprotective, analgesic, and DNA-protective properties. Its bioactive compounds were extracted using ethanol through cold maceration, revealing the presence of alkaloids, phenols, flavonoids, and terpenes, with the extract showing greater analgesic activity than some standard drugs. Similarly,^[52] extracted bioactive compounds from *Psidium guajava* leaves with 70% ethanol via cold maceration to test their antidiabetic potential. Using albino rats and alloxan induction, results showed that the ethanol extract had significant antihyperglycemic effects.

According to,^[53] roots of *Saussurea lappa* were extracted with ethanol using cold maceration to evaluate analgesic and anti-inflammatory properties. The extract demonstrated considerable potential in both activities. Likewise, extracts of *Ocimum sanctum* and neem prepared via cold maceration were tested for antibacterial activity against gram-positive (*Staphylococcus aureus*) and gram-negative (*Escherichia coli*) bacteria. Results confirmed strong antibacterial effects.^[54] Furthermore,^[55] isolated bioactive compounds from *Trachyspermum ammi* L. using cold maceration and reflux methods to test cytotoxicity, acetylcholinesterase (AChE) inhibition, and antioxidant activity. Cold maceration extracts contained the highest phenolic and flavonoid levels and exhibited stronger cytotoxicity and AChE inhibitory activity compared to reflux extracts.

In another study,^[56] screened phytochemicals from *Muntingia calabura* leaves collected in Colombia. Extraction was performed using 96% ethanol via cold maceration, and the leaves were found to contain several valuable phytochemicals. Similarly,^[57] examined *Psidium guajava* (Myrtaceae), a plant widely used in treating inflammation, diabetes, hypertension, wounds, and fever. Phytochemicals in the leaves were extracted with various solvents through cold maceration. The results confirmed that *P. guajava* leaves contained highly valuable bioactive compounds.

4. Petroleum ether was used as a solvent with cold-maceration method

Petroleum ether is a non-polar solvent widely used to extract phytochemicals. In pharmacognosy laboratories, it is commonly applied for plant extraction and separation through chromatography. However, residues of petroleum ether may remain in herbal extracts if not fully removed, which can potentially affect their pharmacological properties.

According to,^[58] petroleum ether extracts of fenugreek obtained through cold maceration were evaluated for anti-inflammatory activity using rats with carrageenan- and formaldehyde-induced paw edema. Gas-liquid chromatography was used for analysis, and the petroleum ether extract showed significant anti-inflammatory effects. The study by.^[59] aimed to evaluate anti-angiogenic and antioxidant activities by extracting *Anabasis articulata* stems with various solvents, including petroleum ether, chloroform, and methanol, using cold maceration. Results revealed higher percentages of anti-angiogenic and antioxidant activity in polar solvents compared to non-polar solvents like petroleum ether.

Orthosiphon stamineus Benth leaves were extracted with methanol, petroleum ether, chloroform, and water using cold maceration.^[60] All solvent extracts exhibited anti-angiogenic and antioxidant activity, but methanol showed the strongest effects due to its polarity. Similarly,^[61] extracted bioactive compounds from *Lantana camara* L. leaves with petroleum ether using cold maceration to assess antioxidant activity and oxidative stability. Antioxidant stability was determined using the Rancimat test. When rich in terpenes, petroleum ether extracts displayed significant antioxidant activity (IC50 value 13 µg/ml) and offered 74.83% greater protection against oxidation compared to standard drugs.

To evaluate antimicrobial activity,^[62] tested petroleum ether extracts of *Platychaete aucheri* (Boiss) against *Pseudomonas aeruginosa* PTCC 1430, *Staphylococcus aureus* PTCC 1431, *Bacillus cereus* PTCC 1247, and *Candida albicans* PTCC 5027. Results showed that petroleum ether and chloroform extracts had stronger bactericidal activity than methanol extracts. According to,^[63] petroleum ether was also used to extract *Cleome viscosa* Linn using cold maceration, along with ethyl acetate, methanol, and aqueous solvents. Biochemical tests indicated that petroleum ether extracts showed better wound-healing activity than other solvents.

In another study,^[64] extracted bioactive compounds from *Amaranthus viridis* and *Amaranthus tricolor* herbs using petroleum ether, chloroform, and ethanol through cold maceration. TLC fingerprint profiling confirmed that petroleum ether and chloroform extracts contained valuable phytochemicals with nutraceutical potential. Similarly, *Achyranthes aspera* roots extracted with petroleum ether demonstrated antibacterial activity, as reported by.^[65]

According to,^[66] petroleum ether extracts of the whole plant *Bergia suffruticosa* were tested for antioxidant, cytotoxic, and anticancer properties. The anticancer activity was measured

using the SRB test against breast carcinoma (MCF-7), prostate carcinoma (PC3), and colon carcinoma (HCT-116) cell lines. The petroleum ether extract exhibited strong antioxidant activity (IC₅₀ = 89.01 µg/ml) and effective anticancer action.

Furthermore,^[67] extracted *Bixa orellana* Linn leaves with petroleum ether via cold maceration. Screening confirmed the presence of valuable phytochemicals, and the petroleum ether extract demonstrated the strongest antibacterial activity against *S. aureus*, with an inhibition zone of 5.6 mm. It also showed general antimicrobial potential. According to,^[68] *Carica papaya* plant parts were extracted with petroleum ether and other solvents to evaluate antimicrobial activity. Results revealed that petroleum ether extracts had the largest inhibition zone (22 ± 0.0 mm) against *S. aureus*, while *E. coli* showed minimal inhibition (0.13 ± 0.00 mm) and *K. pneumoniae* had no inhibition.^[69] extracted phytochemicals from roots and shoots of *Phyllanthus debilis* Klein ex Willd using both polar and non-polar solvents (petroleum ether, chloroform, acetone, ethanol, and water) via cold maceration. The study found that polar solvents exhibited much higher antioxidant activity in the DPPH assay compared to non-polar solvents. Finally,^[70] assessed antimicrobial activity of *Cucumis pustulatus* and *Vernonia schimperi* using extracts prepared with petroleum ether, methanol, and distilled water through cold maceration. Results indicated that extracts from polar solvents possessed stronger antimicrobial activity and more valuable phytochemicals compared to petroleum ether.

5. N-hexane was used as a solvent with cold-maceration method

^[71] used cold maceration to extract bioactive compounds from *Moringa oleifera* roots using n-hexane as the primary solvent. Antibacterial activity was evaluated against clinically isolated *Staphylococcus aureus* using agar-dilution testing. Gas chromatography–mass spectrometry (GC-MS) was performed to analyze the extract and identified 45 compounds.

The major constituents included 9,12-octadecadienoic acid (41.08%), 2-chloroethyl linoleate (41.08%), n-hexadecanoic acid (17.35%), 12-octadecadienoic acid (8.55%), stigmasterol (4.44%), ergost-22-en-3-one (4.44%), and campesterol (3.46%), all of which exhibited significant antibacterial potential.

To determine total phenolic and flavonoid contents,^[72] extracted phytochemicals from *Voacanga africana* using methanol, and further fractionated them into n-hexane, ethyl acetate, and n-butanol fractions via cold maceration. Results indicated that the n-hexane

fraction had the highest total phenolic content (GAE: 116.60 ± 7.95 mg/g) and flavonoid levels. In another study,^[73] extracted bioactive compounds from *Thymelaea hirsuta* L. aerial parts using Soxhlet and cold maceration with n-hexane, ethyl acetate, and methanol. Antioxidant activity was assessed using DPPH and ABTS assays. Methanol cold-maceration extracts exhibited higher levels of bioactive compounds and stronger antioxidant activity than n-hexane and ethyl acetate extracts.

According to,^[74] phytochemicals from *Senna italica* were extracted with n-hexane by cold maceration and analyzed using GC-MS, which revealed valuable constituents such as phytol (3,7,11,15-tetramethyl-1-hexadecen-1-ol) and 1,2-benzenedicarboxylic acid. Similarly,^[75] extracted phytochemicals from the roots and stem bark of *Xylopiya aethiopica* using n-hexane, n-butanol, and petroleum ether. Results showed that n-hexane extracts exhibited weaker antibacterial activity compared to petroleum ether extracts.

Chromophora senegalensis was extracted using cold maceration with n-hexane, ethyl acetate, methanol, and water.^[76] Among the solvents, the n-hexane extract contained the lowest alkaloid levels and showed the least suppression of *Plasmodium falciparum*. Likewise,^[77] studied *Diospyros blancoi*, *Phoenix dactylifera*, and *Morus nigra* for their antibacterial potential against oral pathogens. Extracts were prepared with n-hexane, chloroform, methanol, ethyl acetate, and water. The n-hexane extracts contained the lowest phytochemical levels and showed the weakest antibacterial activity.

According to,^[78] *Fagonia indica* Burm. f. phytochemicals were extracted using water, methanol, chloroform, and n-hexane, and tested for antioxidant and antidiabetic activities.

While several phytochemicals were detected, chloroform and methanol extracts produced substantial results, whereas n-hexane extracts showed minimal activity. Similarly,^[79] extracted phytochemicals from *Mentha piperita* (peppermint) leaves using n-hexane, acetone, dimethyl ether, petroleum ether, chloroform, ethanol, and water. Phytochemicals such as alkaloids, flavonoids, glycosides, terpenoids, saponins, and phenols were detected in all extracts except n-hexane.

As per,^[80] bioactive compounds from *Cordia sebestena* L. were extracted by cold maceration with n-hexane, water, and 70% methanol. TLC profiling revealed 5, 7, and 2 distinct spots for n-hexane, dichloromethane, and methanol extracts, respectively, suggesting different

phytochemical compositions. Finally,^[81] reported that phytochemicals from *Stephania abyssinica* were extracted using cold maceration with methanol, n-hexane, chloroform, and ethyl acetate to evaluate antimalarial activity against *Plasmodium berghei* in mice. Results showed that n-hexane was the least effective chemopreventive agent, while chloroform extracts exhibited the highest chemoprevention (55.80%).

Table IV: Showing the Pharmacological properties of medicinal plants extracted using different solvents with cold maceration method.

Plant name	Plant part	Solvents	Method of extraction	Active phyto compounds	Experimental design	Pharmacological properties	Reference
<i>lantana camara</i>	Root	Methanol extract	Cold-maceration method	Al, Fl, Ste, Sa, Ta, Ter	<i>In-vitro</i>	Anti hyperglycemic anti-diarrheal activities	[05]
<i>New bouldia laevis</i>	Leaf	Methanol extract	Cold-maceration Method		<i>In-vivo</i> (rats)	Anti-hyperglycemic activity	[06]
<i>Combretum hypopilimum</i>	Stem bark	Methanol extract	Cold-maceration Method	Car, Al, Phe, Ste, Ter, Sap, Fla, Tan	<i>In-ivtro</i>	Anti-diarrheal activity	[07]
<i>Napoleona vogelii hook and planch</i>	leaf	70% methanol	Cold-maceration Method	Fla, Sap, Gly, Tan, Anthraquinones.	<i>In-vivo</i> (rats)	Antidiabetic, Hypolipidemic activity	[08]
<i>Lophira lanceolata</i>	Fresh leaf	Methanol extract	Cold-maceration method	Fla, Alk, Oils, Gly, Carbs, Acids, Ter	<i>In-vivo</i> (rodent-mice) & <i>In-vitro</i>	Anti-plasmodial activity, anti-antioxidant activity (in-vitro)	[09]
<i>Musa paradisiaca</i>	Tepal, peel, pulp	Methanol extract	Cold-maceration Method	Fla, Sap, Phe	<i>In-vitro</i>	Anti-inflammatory, Nitric oxide scavenging activity	[10]
<i>Callicarpa arborea</i>	leafs	Methanol extract	Cold-maceration Method	Phe, Fla	<i>In-vitro</i>	Anti-oxidant activity	[11]
<i>Solanum lycopersicum</i>	Fresh fruit	Methanol extract	Cold-maceration Method	Al, Fla, Gly, Sap, Tan, Ste, Phl, Ter, Tan	<i>In-vitro</i>	Anti-microbial activity	[12]
<i>Anabasis atriculata</i>	stem	Methanol extract	Cold maceration method		<i>In-vitro</i>	Antiangiogenesis Antioxidant activity	[13]

<i>Makania micrantha</i>	leafs	Methanol extract	Cold-maceration method	Phe, Fla	<i>In-vitro</i>	Anti-oxidant activity	[14]
<i>schweinfurthian F.Hoffm</i>	Leaf, Stem-bark	Methanol extract	Cold-maceration method		<i>In-vitro</i>	Anti-oxidant activity	[15]
<i>Euphorbia tirucalli</i>	Stem Root	Methanol extract	Cold-maceration method	Alk, Tan, Sap, Fla	<i>In-vitro</i>	Anti-fungal activity Anti-microbial activity	[16]
<i>castnopsis costata</i>	Leaf	Methanol extract	Cold-maceration method	Alk, Fla, Gly, Anthra, Gly, Tan, Tri ter.	<i>In-vitro</i>	Anti-oxidant activity	[17]
<i>Solanum Unigram & solanum xanthocarpum</i>	Leaf fruit	Methanol extract	Cold-maceration method		<i>In-vitro</i>	Antioxidant, Antimicrobial, Antidiabetic and Hemolytic activities	[18]
<i>Lawsonia inermis</i>	leaves	Methanol extract	Cold-maceration method	Tan, Sap, Fla, Alk, Gly, Phe, Anthra	<i>In-vitro</i>		[19]
<i>Moringa stenopetala</i>	leaves	Methanol extract	Cold-maceration method	Fla, Tan, Ter, Sap, Ste, Gly, Alk	<i>In-vivo (swiss albino mice)</i>	Anti-inflammatory, Analgesic activity	[20]
<i>plectranthusamboinicus</i>	leaves	Methanol Extract	Cold-maceration method	tetracontane (16.6%), squalene (15.6%), tetrapentacontane (13.7%), and Phytol (12.9%).	<i>In-vitro</i>	Anti-oxidant activity Antimicrobial activity	[21]
<i>Euphorbia heterophylla & Tithonia diversifolia</i>	leaves	Methanol extract	Cold-maceration method		<i>In-vitro</i>	Anti-bacterial activity	[22]
<i>Coldenia procumbens</i>	leaves	Methanol Extract	Cold-	Ste, Fla, Alk, Phe, Gly	<i>In-vitro</i>	Anti-oxidant activity	[23]

			maceration method				
<i>bryophyllum pinnatum</i>	leaves	Methanol extract	Cold-maceration Method		<i>In-vitro</i>	Anti-diarrheal and antioxidant activity	[24]
<i>Allophylus africanus</i>	leaves	80% hydro-Methanol Extract	Cold-maceration Method	Car, Tan, Ste, Tri, Fla, Alk, Cariat glycoside	<i>In-vivo (Beauv in rat)</i>	Anti-inflammatory activity	[25]
<i>Lupinus arboreus</i>	Leaves	Methanolic extract	Cold-maceration Method		<i>In-vitro</i>	Anti-oxidant activity	[26]
<i>Napoleona vogeliis</i>	Leaves	Methanol extract	Cold-maceration method		<i>In-vitro</i>	Anti-diabetic activity	[27]
<i>Paederia foetida</i>	leaves	Methanol extract	Cold-maceration Method				[28]
<i>Cucurbit Citrullus colocynthis</i>	Leafstem, Root, Tendrils Fruit pulp	Methanolic extract	Cold-maceration Method	Alk, Gly, Tan, Fla, Ste, Phe	<i>In-vitro</i>		[29]
<i>Thespesia populnea</i>	leaves	Methanol extract	Cold-maceration Method	Car, Phe, Fla, Alk, Gly, Sap, Ste, Pro	<i>In-vitro</i>	Anti-inflammatory activity	[30]
<i>Garcinia kola, kola acuminata, kola vera</i>	Kola nuts	Methanol extract	Cold-maceration method	Sap, Gly, Alk, Sap gly, Tan, Ste			[31]
<i>Semenovia suffruticosa</i>	Aerial parts	Methanol extract	Cold-maceration	Z- β -ocimene (25.1%), linalool (17.8%) and β -bisabolol (13.3%)	<i>In-vitro</i>	Cytotoxic, anti-oxidant, antibacterial activity	[32]
<i>Quercus ilex Pinus halepensis</i>	Root, Bark Young ovulate	Methanol extract	Cold-maceration Method	Flavonoids:- Catechin and phenolic acids (4-hydroxybenzoic,	<i>In-vitro</i>	Anti-oxidant, anti-hemolytic, genoprotective effect	[33]

				caffeic, coumaric, ferulic and gentisic acids			
<i>Stachytarpheta indica</i>	leaves	Methanolic extract	Cold-maceration Method	Alk, Sap, Car, Car, Gly, Ter, Tan, Anth, Phe, Fla	<i>In-vitro</i>	Anti-inflammatory activity	[34]
<i>Boswellia dalzielii</i>	Fresh leaf	Mathanolic extract	Cold-maceration method	Alk, Cardiac glycoside, Fla, Sap, Tan, Ter	<i>In-vivo</i>	Anti-diabetic activity	[35]
<i>Cardiosperm halicacabum</i>	Leaves	Methanolic extract	Cold-maceration method	Gly, Tan, Fla, Ter, Phe, Sap	<i>In-vitro</i>	Anti-oxidant activity	[36]
<i>Hibiscus Sabdariffa</i>	Leaf stem calyx of roselle	Methanolic extract	Cold-maceration Method	Phe, Fla, Alk, Antho, Anthra, Cardiac glycosides, Ter, Tan, Ste, Sap	<i>In-vitro</i>	Antioxidant activity	[37]
<i>Fumaria officinalis</i>	leaf	Methanolic extract	Cold-maceration method	Car, Gly, Alk, Fla, Tri, Ste	<i>In-vitro</i>	Antioxidant activity	[38]
<i>Thuja occidentalis</i>	leave	Methanolic extarct	Cold-maceration Method	Alk, Gly, Phe, Flav, Tan	<i>In-vitro</i>	Anti-microbial and Anti-oxidant activity.	[39]
<i>Rhododendron arboreum</i>	leaf	Methanolic extract	Cold-maceration Method	Phe, Alk,	<i>In-vitro</i>	Antioxidant activity	[40]
<i>Achyranthes aspera</i>	Stem leaves	Methanolic extract	Cold-maceration Method		<i>In-vitro</i>	Anti-oxidant activity, anti-inflammatory, anti-microbial and thrombolytic activity	[41]
<i>Fadogia cienkowskii scheinf</i>	leaf	Methanolic extract	Cold-maceration method	Alk, Gly, Tan, Sap, Fla, Ter	<i>In-vitro</i>	Antioxidant activity	[42]

<i>Tinospora cordifolia</i>		Methanolic extract	Cold-maceration method	Alk, coumarin Gly, Reducing sugar, Triterpenes.	<i>In-vitro</i>	Anti-microbial activity, Anti-oxidant and Cytotoxicity activity	[43]
<i>Anabasis aretoides</i> <i>ross & Moq</i>	Aerial	Hydro-ethanolic extract	Cold-maceration method	Cathechic tannins, Sap, Ste.	<i>In-vitro</i>	Antibacterial anti-oxidant activity	[44]
<i>Citrullus colocynthis</i>	Fruit	Hydro-ethanolic extract	Cold-maceration method		<i>In-vivo</i>	Ant-diabetic activity	[45]
<i>Cardiosperm</i>	Leaf	Hydro-ethanolic Extract	Cold-maceration method	Glycosides, Tan, Fla, Phe, Sap	<i>In-vitro</i>	Anti-oxidant activity	[46]
<i>Bryophyllum pinnatum</i>	Aerial part & leaves	Hydro-ethanolic extract	Cold-maceration Method	iperazine, 1-(2-adamantyl)-4-benzoyl,	<i>In-vitro</i>		[47]
<i>Momordica cymbalaria</i>	leaves	Hydro-ethanolic extract	Cold-maceration method	Fla, Phe	<i>In-vitro</i>	Anti-oxidant, anti-diabetic activity.	[48]
<i>Thymelaea hirsuta</i>	aerial parts	Hydro-ethanolic extract	Cold-maceration Method	Phenolic compounds	<i>In-vitro</i>	Anti-oxidant activity	[49]
<i>ANISOCHILUS CARNOSUS</i>	Leaf	Hydro-ethanolic extract	Cold-maceration method		<i>In-vitro</i>	Anti-microbial activity	[50]
<i>Strobilanthes ciliatus</i>	Stem	Hydro-ethanolic extract	Cold-maceration Method	Fla, Phe, Tan, Ste, Tri	<i>In-vivo</i>	Anti-Analgesic activity	[51]
<i>Psidium guajava</i>	leaf	Hydro-ethanolic extract	Cold-maceration method		<i>In-vivo</i>	Anti-hyperglycemic activity	[52]
<i>Saussurea lappa</i>	Root	Ethanolic extract	cold-		<i>In-vitro In-vivo</i>	Analgesic and anti-	[53]

			maceration method			inflammatory activity,	
<i>Ocimum sanctum And azadirachta indica</i>	leaves	Ethanollic extract	Cold-maceration Method	Tan, Sap, Fla, Anthraquinone, Gly, Ste	<i>In-vitro</i>	Anti-microbial activity	[54]
<i>Trachyspermum ammi L.</i>	Fruits	Ethanollic Extract	Cold-maceration Method	Phen, Flav	<i>In-vitro</i>	Cytotoxic, anti-acetylcholinesterase, anti-oxidant activities	[55]
<i>Muntingia calabura</i>	Fruits Brances flowers	Ethanollic extract	Cold-maceration method	sesquiterpene and a lignin (α -eudesmol and sesamin), hexatriacontane, scopolin and flavonoid 3, 5, 7,3',4' Pentahydroxiflavona (quercetin)	<i>In-vitro</i>	Screening of phytochemicals	[56]
<i>Psidium guajava</i>	leaves	Hydro ethanollic extract	Cold-maceration Method				[57]
<i>Fenugreek</i>	Seed powder	Petroleum ether extract	Cold-maceration method	Oleic, linoleic, and linolenic acids.	<i>In-vivo</i>	Anti-inflammatory,	[58]
<i>anabasis articulata</i>	Stem	Petroleum ether extract and methanol extract	Cold-maceration Method		<i>In-vitro</i>	Anti-angiogenic, anti-oxidant activity.	[59]
<i>Orthosiphon stamineus benth</i>	Leaves	Petroleum ether, methanol, chloroform extract	Cold-maceration method		<i>In- vitro</i>	Anti- Angiogenic, Anti-oxidant activity.	[60]
<i>Latana camara</i>	Leaves	Petroleum ether extract	Cold-maceration method	Pentacyclitrite rpenoids, steroid, Iridoid glycosides, Flavonoids aglycones,	<i>In-vitro</i>	Anti-oxidant and oxidative activity.	[61]

				polyphenols			
<i>Platychaete aucheri</i>	Aerial parts	Petroleum ether and chloroform extract	Cold-maceration method		<i>In-vitro</i>	Anti-microbial activity.	[62]
<i>cleome viscoea</i>	Seeds	Petroleum ether extract	Cold-maceration method	Ter, Alk, Phe, Fla, Sap	<i>In-vivo</i>	Wound healing activity	[63]
<i>Amaranthus viridis and Amaranthus tricolor</i>	Different parts	Chloroform and petroleum ether extract	cold-maceration method	Gly, Alk, Fla, Sap, Res, Phy		Nutraceutical potential	[64]
<i>Achyranthus aspera</i>	Root	Petroleum ether, chloroform extract	Cold-maceration method	Pro, Ste	<i>In-vitro</i>	Antimicrobial activity.	[65]
<i>Bergia suffraticosa</i>	Whole plant	Petroleum ether extract	Cold-maceration method		<i>In-vitro</i> <i>In- vivo</i>	Antioxidant and cytotoxicity, anticancer cancer activity	[66]
<i>Bixa orellana .</i>	Leaves	Petroleum ether extract	Cold-maceration Method	Alk, Tri, Ste, Tan, Sap, Fla, Phe, Pro, Gly, Sug, Fats and oils	<i>In-vitro</i>	Anti-bacterial activity	[67]
<i>Caric papaya</i>	leaves	Petroleum ether extract	Cold-maceration method	Alk, Sap, Fla, Ste, Car, Gly, Tan	<i>In-vitro</i>	Anti-microbial activity	[68]
<i>Phyllanthus debilis kleinex</i>	Root Shoot	Petroleum Ether extract	Cold-maceration method	Quinone, cardioglycoside	<i>In-vitro</i>	Antioxidant activity	[69]
<i>Cucumis pustulatus And vernonia schimper</i>			Cold-maceration method				[70]

CONCLUSION

The cold maceration method remains a widely utilized and effective technique for the extraction of bioactive phytoconstituents from various plant materials, especially when thermolabile compounds are of interest. The efficiency of this method is significantly influenced by the polarity of the solvents used, which determines the type and yield of phytochemicals extracted. Polar solvents such as methanol, ethanol and water have demonstrated high efficacy in extracting phenolics, flavonoids, glycosides and alkaloids compounds typically associated with potent antioxidant, antimicrobial, anti-inflammatory and anticancer activities. On the other hand, non-polar solvents like hexane, petroleum ether and chloroform are more suitable for isolating lipophilic constituents such as terpenoids, fatty acids, and certain essential oils, which also possess noteworthy pharmacological effects.

This review emphasizes that the choice of solvent is critical and should be tailored based on the target compound class and intended pharmacological application. Furthermore, the cold maceration technique offers advantages such as simplicity, cost-effectiveness and preservation of heat-sensitive compounds, making it particularly suitable for both laboratory-scale studies and traditional medicinal preparations. In conclusion, cold maceration with appropriate solvent selection remains a valuable tool in natural product research and pharmacognosy, contributing significantly to the discovery and development of plant-based therapeutic agents.

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